

METHODOLOGICAL RULES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF METHODOLOGICAL SKILLS OF FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS

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***Abstract.** In this article, the essence of the topic of developing methodical skills of future elementary school teachers and the content of the concept of methodical skills, the factors necessary for the teacher to become methodically skilled, and the necessary resources about pedagogical prerequisites are theoretically presented. studied.*

***Keywords:** higher education, methodology, qualification, potential, development, independent opinion.*

Today, in addition to material factors in improving the system of higher education and improving the quality of education, the level and potential of developing methodological skills of students are also important. In order to determine appropriate approaches to the development of students' methodical skills in higher education institutions, we analyze several programs for teaching students and pay special attention to the methodical activities carried out on the basis of them. The potential of future elementary school teachers to think, mental development, to form the potential of self-awareness, to teach them to feel the reality of material existence, to understand the opinions of others, to express their personal opinions orally and in writing should achieve the formation of feelings of achievement.

The decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 9, 2019 "State support for the further development of mathematics education and sciences, as well as measures to fundamentally improve the activities of the Institute of Mathematics named after V.I. Romanovsky of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan "about" Decree No. PQ-4387[2], Decree No. PF-4708[4] of 2019 "On measures to improve the quality of education and development of scientific research in the field of mathematics" dated May 7, 2020 Decree No. PF-5712 dated April 29 "On approval of the concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" [1] and other normative legal documents related to the topic of the dissertation are the theoretical basis of this dissertation work.

It is necessary to start reforming the education sector, first of all, from primary education. It is known that the most mature and experienced coaches should be attached to primary classes, where a child's outlook and potential are formed. Due to this necessity, radical reforms of school education, as well as higher education, are being carried out. In addition to material factors in improving the quality and effectiveness of education, the development of methodological skills of future primary school teachers is of urgent importance. Because, the era itself demands that future elementary school teachers prepare their competitive personnel according to the requirements of today's era.

It is important to approach the development of methodical skills of future primary school teachers based on the requirements of the time. In order to improve the methodological skills of teachers, they must have the necessary pedagogical knowledge (teacher's work, characteristics of his pedagogical activity, communication, personality, psychological development of students, their age characteristics, psychology, pedagogical information), skills (behavior performed at a sufficiently high level) should be formed.

The change in the requirements for the methodological skills of future primary school teachers can be determined by two main educational paradigms: in particular, humanism manifested in the person-oriented approach and socialization of education.

According to M.E. Jumaev, "mathematical methodical training of future elementary school teachers - methodology and history of scientific research in mathematics, as a component of humanistically oriented primary mathematics education, the formation of inquisitive mathematical activity in students was envisaged".

B.S. Abdullaeva's scientific works contain the following comments: "The professional potential and level of education of a primary school teacher, knowledge of child psychology, modern primary education methods are important in improving the quality of primary education. It is desirable to form the necessary skills in primary school students, to bring the quality and effectiveness of primary education to a new level, and to introduce modern teaching tools into practice".

In developing the methodology for the development of methodological skills of future primary school teachers, we proceeded from the following rules:

- In order to develop methodical skills in the process of teaching mathematics, it is important to properly organize the educational activities of elementary school teachers in the lower courses of education due to the superiority of their educational activities over professional-methodical activities;

- The main content, purpose and result of the educational activity is to acquire knowledge, methods of action and develop the skills to perform these methods.

In this regard, since the science of mathematics teaching methodology in primary education is interpreted through the types of professional-methodical actions, it is necessary to include the methods of mastering the methods of methodical operations in the content of the training of future primary school teachers;

The importance of starting the formation of methodological skills in the mathematics training course of the higher educational institution of pedagogy for primary school teachers to learn the content of the subject of mathematics, which does not go beyond the scope of educational activities and is similar / analogous to primary school determines the need to define such educational tasks that exist in the practical activity of the mathematics teaching methodology of teachers. Learning mathematics should not be replaced by learning methodology. Here we are talking only about possible and necessary assimilation of the elements of methodical actions/movements in the process of learning the method of developing methodical skills of future primary school teachers.

Therefore, as components of the competence studied in the research work, we distinguish the following:

- the ability to create new ones by analyzing previously solved problems/exercises/tasks;

- the ability to organize previously solved problem/exercise/task components into similar problems/exercises/tasks by expanding the existing content;

- the ability to organize mathematical problems/exercises/tasks according to the stages of learning a didactic unit (the ability to organize previously solved problems/exercises/tasks for different stages of working on a didactic unit).

In developing the methodological skills of future primary school teachers, taking into account that the development of students' methodological skills is more closely related to mathematics, the development of mathematical thinking of future teachers is also an important factor.

Therefore, in the process of working on the development of methodological skills of future elementary school teachers, it is necessary to pay special attention to the formation of skills and abilities to apply the learned knowledge in the practical process, not only to give students scientific knowledge. In particular, practical teaching of elementary education subjects, regular and consistent teaching, teaching on the basis of examples and special exercises, and performing practical tasks on their own, such as preventing and correcting various mistakes. It is important to absorb through. Taking into account the age and psychological characteristics of students, it helps to master all the subjects of the curriculum, independent thinking, free expression of opinion, listening to the opinion of others, reasoning, distinguishing the most important ones from them, giving one's own opinion. It is being studied as a requirement of the present day to promote, to prove it, to teach it to generalize and conclude, to arouse the interest of the teacher in using the language material, to create the need to use it in practice.

As mentioned above, a number of tasks regarding the development of methodical skills of future primary school teachers are highlighted.

- diagnosis of development of methodical skills of future elementary school teachers and formation of their readiness for professional and professional activity;

- to teach the basics of research in the development of professional and professional activities of future primary school teachers in the development of their methodical skills;

- creating conditions for future primary school teachers to reveal and implement their methodical skills;

- training of specialists who have design work skills, who can develop precise scientific and practical measures in production, and who have self-management skills;

- ensuring the integration of educational activities and methodological skills of future primary school teachers;

The formation of these tasks by primary school teachers directly affects the development of educated and intellectually developed personnel in the future.

In conclusion, the research of the given scientific problem showed other directions of its study, among them:

- the possibilities of using educational tasks for the development of methodical activity methods and the features of the system of methodical tasks in the implementation of differentiated teaching;

- use of educational tasks and methodical tasks that implement them in the development of other methodical skills;

- to consider the features of using generalized methods and methods of methodical activity at different stages of development;

- it was necessary to research the characteristics of the subject/subject content of the activity when studying the mathematics teaching methodology of the future primary education teachers.

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